

Mapping Sateri Cult of Konkan: An Exercise in Cultural Mapping

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Abstract:

A map is a graphical representation depicting associations among multiple spatial elements. Spatial elements that are intangible need special attention and efforts to be placed on map as they are abstract in nature.

Culture is a topic of concern for many scholars of all fields for a long time. However, it is an especially difficult term to define. We propose that culture is a network of traits that could be learned, through interactions and/or consequential to traditions.

A good cultural map is a valuable tool for identifying a community's intangible assets. When it comes to planning the resources, identifying efficiencies and links between cultural assets and economic progress and implementing ideas for overall development of a community, such an exercise aids in understanding common aspirations and values that community members cherish, in order to chalk out strategy which is compatible to and adheres processes of reconstruction such as globalisation.

Current Paper reveals spatial spread of religious belief, persistent in Sindhudurg district of Maharashtra and entire state of Goa and its relation with larger cultural spaces. Sateri worship is actually the embodiment of process of procreation that has developed over the centuries and this belief is so deep rooted that it has reached a level of a separate cult.

Key Words:

Culture, Mapping, Intangible, Embodiment, Konkan.

Introduction:

Maps are versatile. A map can be loaded with many kinds of data that can then be unpacked, isolated and reconfigured. As for its form, the choice ranges from an artist's hand-crafted interpretation to the most erudite, hyper-linked, web-ready, multi-media anthology. On both counts of information and form, a map has much greater potential than an inventory as it communicates rapidly and in a holistic fashion; a web-based map can be multidimensional and can have a very broad reach. A broadly-based mapping exercise for purposes of investigating or creating an identity profile of the community is enriching, informative and useful. One member of the Creative City network of Canada commented, he has "got more political mileage out of that than just about anything else." It can give a boost to advocacy activities, both yours and those of the community. (Cultural Mapping Toolkit, 2010)

The process of mapping by itself draws attention to the existence and importance of cultural resources. The results point out problems to be solved or strengths to build upon. The publicity surrounding the announcement of results can be used to bring the issues up on the public agenda. The various community sectors can also rely on the results to support their own arguments for increased support.

Culture is something that we learn through experience and also through formal education. But, no culture in the world has fixed standards as no social phenomenon can have a fixed ontology. So, change is inherent to any culture. Cultural mapping enables us to understand and share variation in culture; to re-think history; and to promote creativity and development.

Culture of Konkan is unique in many ways. The annual festival held once in a year in the honour of the village deity, is an important event in the life of the rural masses when they can have entertainment and cultural enjoyment. Even in the age of the modern entertainments, these festivals of village deities have retained their importance in the life of the common people. According to the Census Report of 1961, in Konkan 1629 festivals were held every year, out of which 1409 festivals were held in the rural areas. The artistic life in Konkan has developed on the foundation of religious life. (Gazetteer, 1996)

Study Area:

Sateri worship has spread over entire Sindhudurg District of Konkan and a few places in Ratnagiri district. Entire state of Goa, south of Sindhudurg district is also under the influence of this cult. Spatially the cult is connected with other districts of the state such as Pune, Satara

and Kolhapur and southern states of Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka, though the embodiment of cult goddess is sometimes different. If researched deeply, one may find connection of the cult with Shaktism which is spread nationwide and is embodied differently in different assemblages of culture.

Objectives:

The exercise was undertaken with following objectives in mind

1. Defining the cult
2. Defining spatial reach of the cult
3. Identifying Spatial links of the cult
4. Analysing efficacy of the cult as a cultural asset.

Methodology:

Primary data was collected through

unstructured interviews and field observation.

History of the region as well as history of religious faiths have been gathered by secondary sources such as census books, gazetteers and journal articles as well as books on archaeology as well as mythology.

Both the data primary as well as secondary was then analysed and maps were produced using satellite imageries from the google earth in MapInfo Professional -12.0.

Findings:

Sateri Cult is deeply rooted in culture of Konkan. However, it is found in its most original form in entire Sindhudurg District and state of Goa. Whereas other districts of Konkan viz. Raigad, Thane and Palghar have predominantly more personified form of the cult. In Ratnagiri district few places show the original form of sateri worship.

It has been noticed that very few times feminine character of the divinity gets transformed into masculinity. and the same anthill or termite hill is referred to as bhombada or bhomdev. Similar practice

is found near Jejuri, on banks of river Karha where termite hill is referred with masculine name “Adimailar”. (Dhere, 2011, p. 176)

In Andhra Pradesh and in Tamil Nadu Anthill worship do exist but, it is accompanied by personified idols of the divinity.

In Karnataka Personified idols are preferred over natural anthills though the idea that anthill is original form of the divinity is still maintained in folksongs and folk literature.

In all forms the divinity is believed to have supernatural powers of procreation.

Conclusion:

Sateri Cult of Konkan is one of the oldest forms of nature worship. The termite hill is believed to bring up the primordial water deep down from the womb of mother earth. (Gawade, 2018, p. 34)

With advancement of science, we have discovered many facts about most important position of termite hill in maintenance of surrounding ecosystem. Ancestral practices of this region have unknowing helped all these years to conserve the ecosystem. (Irwin, 1982), (Ali, Sheridan, French, & Berhan, 2013), (Chaudhury, Khirod, & L. Nonglait, 2017).

Sindhudurg, which has been declared as a tourism district, can develop a sound cultural base that is preserving environmental base which in turn may further boost tourism sector of the region and this may help bring in prosperity and overall development of the region.

In other districts of Konkan where the divinity is personified can also think about developing religious practices as cultural base of tourism.

Dr. Madhav Gadgil's report in 2011 (Gadgil, 2011) on Environmental conditions of western ghat urged to stop any development projects that may bring devastation to world heritage region of Western Ghats. So, the most eco-friendly solution left for development of the region is developing Tourism. And we opine that Cultural practices can provide strong and infinite base for development of the region.

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